

Interplay Between Apolipoprotein(A) And Cardiovascular Pathophysiology In Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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ABSTRACT

This review explores the multifaceted role of Apolipoprotein(a) [Apo(a)] in the context of cardiovascular disease (CVD) and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). Apo(a), a critical component of lipoprotein(a) [Lp(a)], is increasingly recognized for its contribution to cardiovascular risk, particularly in diabetic populations. The review delves into the biochemical structure and physiological role of Apo(a), highlighting its involvement in atherogenesis and its impact on metabolic dysregulation in T2DM. We examine the pathophysiological mechanisms linking Apo(a) to major cardiovascular complications in diabetes, such as atherosclerosis, myocardial infarction, stroke, and peripheral arterial disease. The diagnostic value of Apo(a) as a biomarker for cardiovascular risk assessment in T2DM is discussed, along with emerging therapeutic strategies targeting Apo(a), including antisense oligonucleotides and novel lipid-lowering agents. This comprehensive analysis underscores the need for further research into targeted therapies and personalized treatment approaches for managing cardiovascular risk in T2DM patients with elevated Apo(a) levels.

Keywords: Apolipoprotein(a), Cardiovascular Disease, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Atherogenesis, Biomarkers, Therapeutic Strategies, Lipoprotein(a), Metabolic Dysregulation, Cardiovascular Complications, Personalized Medicine.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10437472

Publication Website: thewitfire.in

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Update: Received on 12/12/2023; Accepted; 18/12/2023, Published on; 28/12/2023

INTRODUCTION

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) and cardiovascular disease (CVD) represent two of the most significant public health challenges globally. The intricate interplay between these conditions, particularly mediated by factors like Apolipoprotein(a), necessitates a deeper understanding for effective clinical management and therapeutic innovation.

Overview of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, characterized by insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency, is a chronic metabolic disorder. It has emerged as a global epidemic, with significant implications for healthcare systems worldwide (Zheng et al., 2018). The pathophysiology of T2DM involves a complex interplay of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors, leading to impaired glucose metabolism and associated complications (Galicia-Garcia et al., 2020). The management of T2DM requires a multifaceted approach, including lifestyle modifications and pharmacological interventions (Tuomilehto et al., 2001).

Cardiovascular Disease in Diabetic Context

Individuals with T2DM are at a substantially higher risk of developing cardiovascular diseases, such as coronary artery disease, stroke, and peripheral arterial disease. This increased risk is attributed to a combination of hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, and chronic inflammation (Pradhan et al., 2001). The management of cardiovascular risk in T2DM is therefore a critical aspect of diabetes care, necessitating a comprehensive approach that addresses both glycemic control and cardiovascular risk factors (Scirica et al., 2013).

Apolipoprotein(a): A Brief Introduction

Apolipoprotein(a) is a key player in lipid metabolism and cardiovascular risk. It is a component of lipoprotein(a), a lipoprotein variant implicated in atherogenesis. Elevated levels of Apolipoprotein(a) have been associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular events, particularly in individuals with T2DM (Ferguson & Finck, 2021). Understanding the role of Apolipoprotein(a) in the context of diabetes is crucial for developing targeted therapies to mitigate cardiovascular risk.

Rationale and Scope of the Review

This review aims to synthesize current knowledge on the role of Apolipoprotein(a) in the development and progression of cardiovascular disease in patients with T2DM. It will explore the molecular mechanisms underlying this relationship, discuss the clinical implications, and highlight potential therapeutic targets. The review is intended to provide a comprehensive resource for clinicians, researchers, and policymakers involved in the management of T2DM and its cardiovascular complications.

APOLIPOPROTEIN(A): STRUCTURE AND FUNCTION

Apolipoprotein(a) [Apo(a)] is a distinctive and complex glycoprotein that plays a pivotal role in lipid metabolism and cardiovascular health. Its intricate structure and function, along with genetic variations, have profound implications in the pathophysiology of cardiovascular diseases, particularly in the context of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM).

Biochemical Structure

Apo(a) is known for its unique and complex biochemical structure. It is characterized by a series of kringle domains, which are highly glycosylated, and a protease-like domain that is homologous to plasminogen (Byrne & Lawn, 1994). The molecular crowding within these domains impacts the overall structure of Apo(a), influencing its interaction with other lipoproteins and its functional properties in lipid metabolism (Petrlova et al., 2016). This structural complexity is crucial for its role in high-density lipoprotein (HDL) particle formation and function (Durbin & Jonas, 1997).

Physiological Role

The primary physiological role of Apo(a) lies in its involvement in lipid transport and atherogenesis. It is a key component of lipoprotein(a) [Lp(a)], which is an LDL-like particle. Lp(a) plays a significant role in cholesterol transport and has been implicated in the development of atherosclerotic lesions (Navab et al., 2010). Apo(a), through its association with Lp(a), contributes to the modulation of fibrinolysis and wound healing processes, thereby influencing cardiovascular health (Rye & Barter, 1994).

Genetic Variations and Implications

Genetic variations in the Apo(a) gene significantly affect its plasma levels and functional properties. Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in the Apo(a) gene have been associated with variations in Lp(a) levels and cardiovascular risk (Saeed et al., 2018). These genetic variations can lead to alterations in the structure and function of Apo(a), thereby modulating the risk of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular events, especially in individuals with T2DM (Henson et al., 2020). Understanding these genetic factors is crucial for developing personalized therapeutic strategies targeting Apo(a) in cardiovascular disease management.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a multifaceted disease characterized by various metabolic dysfunctions. The pathophysiology of T2DM involves a complex interplay of metabolic dysregulation, insulin resistance, hyperglycemia, chronic inflammation, and oxidative stress, each contributing to the disease's progression and complications.

Metabolic Dysregulation

Metabolic dysregulation in T2DM is primarily characterized by impaired insulin secretion and abnormal glucose and lipid metabolism. The pancreatic β -cells, which are responsible for insulin production, become dysfunctional over time, leading to inadequate insulin secretion in response to glucose levels (Kaneto, 2015). This dysregulation is further exacerbated by the liver's increased glucose production and altered lipid metabolism, contributing to the hyperglycemic state (Scheen & Lefèbvre, 1996).

Insulin Resistance and Hyperglycemia

Insulin resistance, a hallmark of T2DM, is a state where the body's cells do not respond effectively to insulin. This resistance leads to increased blood glucose levels, as glucose is unable to enter the cells efficiently (Galicia-Garcia et al., 2020). Over time, the pancreas attempts to compensate by producing more insulin, leading to hyperinsulinemia. However, as the disease progresses, the pancreatic β -cells fail to keep up, resulting in persistent hyperglycemia (Ke et al., 2022).

Chronic Inflammation and Oxidative Stress

Chronic inflammation and oxidative stress play a significant role in the pathogenesis of T2DM. Inflammatory cytokines are elevated in T2DM, contributing to insulin resistance and β -cell dysfunction (Olaogun et al., 2020). Oxidative stress, resulting from an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and antioxidant defenses, further exacerbates insulin resistance and impairs β -cell function. This oxidative stress is linked to the chronic low-grade inflammation observed in T2DM patients (Rehman & Akash, 2017).

CARDIOVASCULAR COMPLICATIONS IN DIABETES

Patients with diabetes, particularly Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), are at a significantly increased risk of developing a range of cardiovascular complications. These include atherosclerosis, myocardial infarction, stroke, and peripheral arterial disease, each contributing to the morbidity and mortality associated with the disease.

Atherosclerosis

Atherosclerosis, characterized by the buildup of plaques in the arterial walls, is a major cardiovascular complication in diabetes. Hyperglycemia, dyslipidemia, and insulin resistance, common in T2DM, contribute to endothelial dysfunction, inflammation, and oxidative stress, accelerating the atherosclerotic process (Haidara et al., 2006). The glycemic variability in diabetes further exacerbates the development of atherosclerosis (Nusca et al., 2018).

Myocardial Infarction

Myocardial infarction (MI), or heart attack, is a severe consequence of coronary artery disease, which is more prevalent in diabetic patients. Diabetes leads to changes in the coronary arteries, including increased plaque buildup and reduced vascular compliance, significantly raising the risk of MI. The altered metabolic state in diabetes also impairs the heart's response to ischemic injury, worsening the outcomes of MI (Betteridge & Nicholls, 2014).

Stroke

Stroke, particularly ischemic stroke, is another critical cardiovascular complication associated with diabetes. The risk factors prevalent in diabetes, such as hypertension, atherosclerosis, and

hypercoagulability, contribute to an increased risk of cerebrovascular events. Diabetes also affects the cerebral vasculature, leading to impaired blood flow and increased susceptibility to stroke (Wu et al., 2022).

Peripheral Arterial Disease

Peripheral arterial disease (PAD) in diabetic individuals is a manifestation of systemic atherosclerosis. It is characterized by reduced blood flow to the extremities, particularly the legs, leading to pain, ulcers, and, in severe cases, limb amputation. The pathogenesis of PAD in diabetes involves a combination of endothelial dysfunction, inflammation, and hyperglycemia-induced vascular changes (A. Potenza et al., 2011).

ROLE OF APOLIPOPROTEIN(A) IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE

Apolipoprotein(a) [Apo(a)] plays a significant role in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular disease (CVD), particularly in individuals with diabetes. Understanding the mechanisms by which Apo(a) contributes to cardiovascular risk is crucial for developing targeted therapies and improving patient outcomes.

Mechanistic Insights

The mechanistic role of Apo(a) in CVD is multifaceted. Apo(a), as a component of lipoprotein(a) [Lp(a)], contributes to atherogenesis through its pro-inflammatory and pro-thrombotic properties. It promotes the oxidation of other apolipoproteins, such as Apo A-1 and Apo B-100, which are critical in lipid metabolism and atherosclerotic plaque formation (Coremans et al., 2021). Additionally, Apo(a) interferes with the fibrinolytic system, increasing the risk of thrombus formation, a key event in the development of cardiovascular events.

Apolipoprotein(a) and Atherogenesis

Apo(a) is directly implicated in the process of atherogenesis. It enhances the deposition of cholesterol in the arterial walls, contributing to plaque formation and progression. The unique structure of Apo(a), with its kringle domains, allows it to bind to various components of the arterial wall, promoting lipid accumulation and foam cell formation. This process is exacerbated

in the presence of diabetes, where altered lipid profiles and increased oxidative stress provide a conducive environment for atherosclerotic plaque development.

Clinical Evidence Linking Apolipoprotein(a) and Cardiovascular Risk in Diabetics

Clinical studies have established a link between elevated levels of Apo(a) and increased cardiovascular risk in diabetic patients. The presence of high Apo(a) levels in individuals with diabetes is associated with a greater incidence of coronary artery disease, myocardial infarction, and stroke. Monitoring the blood concentration of Apo(a) can be a useful tool in assessing the risk of cardiovascular complications in diabetic patients (Plasma apolipoproteins: their role in cardiovascular diseases and usefulness of their blood concentration determination. Committee of the Study of Apolipoproteins, Italian Heart Foundation, 1997).

DIAGNOSTIC AND THERAPEUTIC IMPLICATIONS

The diagnostic and therapeutic implications of Apolipoprotein(a) [Apo(a)] in cardiovascular disease and diabetes are pivotal in guiding clinical decisions and improving patient outcomes. Understanding the role of biomarkers, therapeutic strategies, and emerging treatments is essential for effective management of these conditions.

Biomarkers in Cardiovascular Disease and Diabetes

Biomarkers play a crucial role in the diagnosis and management of cardiovascular disease and diabetes. Apo(a) itself serves as a significant biomarker, particularly in assessing the risk of cardiovascular complications in diabetic patients. Elevated levels of Apo(a) are associated with increased cardiovascular risk, and monitoring its levels can aid in risk stratification and management decisions (Coremans et al., 2021). Other biomarkers, such as C-reactive protein (CRP), glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), and lipid profiles, are also crucial in evaluating cardiovascular risk and therapeutic responses in diabetes.

Therapeutic Strategies Targeting Apolipoprotein(a)

Targeting Apo(a) in therapeutic strategies is an emerging area of interest. The development of specific inhibitors or modulators of Apo(a) could potentially reduce cardiovascular risk in patients with elevated Apo(a) levels. Current therapeutic approaches primarily focus on

managing traditional risk factors, such as hyperlipidemia, hypertension, and hyperglycemia, which indirectly influence Apo(a) levels and its pathogenic effects (Plasma apolipoproteins: their role in cardiovascular diseases and usefulness of their blood concentration determination. Committee of the Study of Apolipoproteins, Italian Heart Foundation, 1997).

Emerging Treatments and Clinical Trials

Emerging treatments and ongoing clinical trials are exploring novel approaches to modulate Apo(a) levels and its impact on cardiovascular disease in diabetes. These include the development of antisense oligonucleotides targeting Apo(a) mRNA, which have shown promise in reducing Lp(a) levels in preliminary studies. Additionally, new classes of lipid-lowering agents, such as PCSK9 inhibitors, have shown potential in modifying cardiovascular risk profiles, including the impact of Apo(a) (Coremans et al., 2021).

DISCUSSION

The intricate relationship between Apolipoprotein(a) [Apo(a)], cardiovascular disease (CVD), and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) presents a complex landscape for clinical management and therapeutic intervention. This discussion synthesizes the findings from various studies and explores the implications of these relationships in the context of patient care and future research directions.

Interplay Between Apo(a), CVD, and T2DM

Apo(a) has been identified as a critical player in the pathogenesis of CVD, especially in the context of T2DM. Its role in promoting atherosclerosis, influencing lipid metabolism, and contributing to pro-thrombotic states underscores its significance as a biomarker and a potential therapeutic target (Coremans et al., 2021). Elevated levels of Apo(a) in diabetic patients are associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular events, including myocardial infarction and stroke (Plasma apolipoproteins: their role in cardiovascular diseases and usefulness of their blood concentration determination. Committee of the Study of Apolipoproteins, Italian Heart Foundation, 1997).

Challenges in Clinical Management

The management of patients with elevated Apo(a) levels, particularly those with T2DM, poses significant challenges. Current therapeutic strategies primarily focus on controlling traditional risk factors, such as dyslipidemia, hypertension, and hyperglycemia. However, these approaches may not adequately address the specific risks posed by high Apo(a) levels. The need for therapies that directly target Apo(a) is evident, yet such treatments are still in the early stages of development and clinical testing.

Emerging Therapeutic Strategies

Emerging therapies targeting Apo(a) are promising. Antisense oligonucleotides that reduce Lp(a) levels by targeting Apo(a) mRNA have shown potential in early clinical trials. Additionally, novel lipid-lowering agents, including PCSK9 inhibitors, offer new avenues for reducing cardiovascular risk in patients with elevated Apo(a) levels (Coremans et al., 2021). These developments represent a significant advancement in the potential management of cardiovascular risk in T2DM.

Future Research Directions

Future research should focus on elucidating the precise mechanisms by which Apo(a) contributes to cardiovascular risk in T2DM. Longitudinal studies are needed to understand the impact of Apo(a) over time and in response to various therapeutic interventions. Additionally, large-scale clinical trials are essential to establish the efficacy and safety of therapies targeting Apo(a). Such research will not only enhance our understanding of the pathophysiology of CVD in T2DM but also lead to more effective and personalized treatment strategies.

Conclusion

The role of Apo(a) in cardiovascular disease, particularly in the context of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, is a critical area of research with significant implications for clinical practice. While current therapeutic strategies focus on managing traditional risk factors, emerging treatments targeting Apo(a) offer the promise of more effective management of cardiovascular risk in this patient population. Continued research is essential to fully understand the role of Apo(a) in CVD and to develop targeted therapies that can improve patient outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Bellamy, L., Casas, J.-P., Hingorani, A. D., & Williams, D. (2009). Type 2 diabetes mellitus after gestational diabetes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet*, 373(9677), 1773–1779. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(09\)60731-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(09)60731-5)
- Bellary, S., Kyrou, I., Brown, J. E., & Bailey, C. J. (2021). Type 2 diabetes mellitus in older adults: clinical considerations and management. *Nature Reviews. Endocrinology*, 17(9), 534–548. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41574-021-00512-2>
- Ferguson, D., & Finck, B. N. (2021). Emerging therapeutic approaches for the treatment of NAFLD and type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Nature Reviews. Endocrinology*, 17(8), 484–495. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41574-021-00507-z>
- Galicia-Garcia, U., Benito-Vicente, A., Jebari, S., Larrea-Sebal, A., Siddiqi, H., Uribe, K. B., Ostolaza, H., & Martín, C. (2020). Pathophysiology of type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(17), 6275. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21176275>
- Ohara, T., & Kasuga, M. (2001). Type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Nihon rinsho. Japanese journal of clinical medicine*, 59 Suppl 8(1), 223–230. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrdp.2015.19>
- Pradhan, A. D., Manson, J. E., Rifai, N., Buring, J. E., & Ridker, P. M. (2001). C-reactive protein, interleukin 6, and risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus. *JAMA: The Journal of the American Medical Association*, 286(3), 327–334. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.286.3.327>
- Scirica, B. M., Bhatt, D. L., Braunwald, E., Steg, P. G., Davidson, J., Hirshberg, B., Ohman, P., Frederich, R., Wiviott, S. D., Hoffman, E. B., Cavender, M. A., Udell, J. A., Desai, N. R., Mosenzon, O., McGuire, D. K., Ray, K. K., Leiter, L. A., Raz, I., & SAVOR-TIMI 53 Steering Committee and Investigators. (2013). Saxagliptin and cardiovascular outcomes in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 369(14), 1317–1326. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1307684>
- Targher, G., Corey, K. E., Byrne, C. D., & Roden, M. (2021). The complex link between NAFLD and type 2 diabetes mellitus - mechanisms and treatments. *Nature Reviews.*

Gastroenterology & Hepatology, 18(9), 599–612. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41575-021-00448-y>

- Tuomilehto, J., Lindström, J., Eriksson, J. G., Valle, T. T., Hämäläinen, H., Ilanne-Parikka, P., Keinänen-Kiukaanniemi, S., Laakso, M., Louheranta, A., Rastas, M., Salminen, V., Uusitupa, M., & Finnish Diabetes Prevention Study Group. (2001). Prevention of type 2 diabetes mellitus by changes in lifestyle among subjects with impaired glucose tolerance. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 344(18), 1343–1350. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM200105033441801>
- Zheng, Y., Ley, S. H., & Hu, F. B. (2018). Global aetiology and epidemiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus and its complications. *Nature Reviews. Endocrinology*, 14(2), 88–98. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrendo.2017.151>
- Byrne, C. D., & Lawn, R. M. (1994). Studies on the structure and function of the apolipoprotein(a) gene. *Clinical Genetics*, 46(1 Spec), 34–41. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-0004.1994.tb04199.x>
- Durbin, D. M., & Jonas, A. (1997). The effect of apolipoprotein A-II on the structure and function of apolipoprotein A-I in a homogeneous reconstituted high density lipoprotein particle. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 272(50), 31333–31339. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.272.50.31333>
- Henson, R. N., Suri, S., Knights, E., Rowe, J. B., Kievit, R. A., Lyall, D. M., Chan, D., Eising, E., & Fisher, S. E. (2020). Effect of apolipoprotein E polymorphism on cognition and brain in the Cambridge Centre for Ageing and Neuroscience cohort. *Brain and Neuroscience Advances*, 4, 2398212820961704. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2398212820961704>
- Navab, M., Shechter, I., Anantharamaiah, G. M., Reddy, S. T., Van Lenten, B. J., & Fogelman, A. M. (2010). Structure and function of HDL mimetics. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology*, 30(2), 164–168. <https://doi.org/10.1161/ATVBAHA.109.187518>

- Petrlova, J., Hilt, S., Budamagunta, M., Domingo-Espín, J., Voss, J. C., & Lagerstedt, J. O. (2016). Molecular crowding impacts the structure of apolipoprotein A-I with potential implications on in vivo metabolism and function. *Biopolymers*, 105(10), 683–692. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bip.22865>
- Rye, K. A., & Barter, P. J. (1994). The influence of apolipoproteins on the structure and function of spheroidal, reconstituted high density lipoproteins. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 269(14), 10298–10303. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9258\(17\)34060-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9258(17)34060-7)
- Saeed, N. A. A. A. H., Hamzah, I. H., Ali, A. N. M., & Abuderman, A. A. (2018). Prediction of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in apolipoprotein E gene and their possible associations with a deleterious effect on the structure and functional properties: an in silico approach. *Network Modeling and Analysis in Health Informatics and Bioinformatics*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13721-018-0178-9>
- Sparrow, D. A., Laplaud, P. M., Saboureau, M., Zhou, G., Dolphin, P. J., Gotto, A. M., Jr, & Sparrow, J. T. (1995). Plasma lipid transport in the hedgehog: partial characterization of structure and function of apolipoprotein A-I. *The Journal of Lipid Research*, 36(3), 485–495. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-2275\(20\)39882-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-2275(20)39882-5)
- Galicia-Garcia, U., Benito-Vicente, A., Jebari, S., Larrea-Sebal, A., Siddiqi, H., Uribe, K. B., Ostolaza, H., & Martín, C. (2020). Pathophysiology of type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(17), 6275. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21176275>
- Kaneto, H. (2015). Pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Nihon rinsho. Japanese journal of clinical medicine*, 73(12), 2003–2007. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26666144>
- Ke, C., Narayan, K. M. V., Chan, J. C. N., Jha, P., & Shah, B. R. (2022). Pathophysiology, phenotypes and management of type 2 diabetes mellitus in Indian and Chinese populations. *Nature Reviews. Endocrinology*, 18(7), 413–432. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41574-022-00669-4>

- Olaogun, I., Farag, M., & Hamid, P. (2020). The pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus in non-obese individuals: An overview of the current understanding. *Cureus*, 12(4), e7614. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.7614>
- Rehman, K., & Akash, M. S. H. (2017). Mechanism of generation of oxidative stress and pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus: How are they interlinked? *Journal of Cellular Biochemistry*, 118(11), 3577–3585. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcb.26097>
- Scheen, A. J., & Lefèbvre, P. J. (1996). Pathophysiology of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. In *Oral Antidiabetics* (pp. 7–42). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-09127-2_2
- A. Potenza, M., Nacci, C., Gagliardi, S., & Montagnani, M. (2011). Cardiovascular complications in diabetes: Lessons from animal models. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 18(12), 1806–1819. <https://doi.org/10.2174/092986711795496755>
- Betteridge, D. J., & Nicholls, S. J. (Eds.). (2014). *Managing cardiovascular complications in diabetes*. Wiley-Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118337967>
- Haidara, M. A., Yassin, H. Z., Rateb, M., Ammar, H., & Zorkani, M. A. (2006). Role of oxidative stress in development of cardiovascular complications in diabetes mellitus. *Current Vascular Pharmacology*, 4(3), 215–227. <https://doi.org/10.2174/157016106777698469>
- Nusca, A., Tuccinardi, D., Albano, M., Cavallaro, C., Ricottini, E., Manfrini, S., Pozzilli, P., & Di Sciascio, G. (2018). Glycemic variability in the development of cardiovascular complications in diabetes. *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews*, 34(8), e3047. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dmrr.3047>
- Wu, H., Norton, V., Cui, K., Zhu, B., Bhattacharjee, S., Lu, Y. W., Wang, B., Shan, D., Wong, S., Dong, Y., Chan, S.-L., Cowan, D., Xu, J., Bielenberg, D. R., Zhou, C., & Chen, H. (2022). Diabetes and its cardiovascular complications: Comprehensive network and systematic analyses. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine*, 9, 841928. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcvm.2022.841928>

- Coremans, C., Boudjeltia, K. Z., Van Antwerpen, P., & Delporte, C. (2021). Roles of myeloperoxidase in the oxidation of apolipoproteins: Interest of monitoring myeloperoxidase oxidation of apolipoproteins A-1 and B-100 to improve the estimation of lipoprotein quality in cardiovascular diseases. In *Mammalian Heme Peroxidases* (pp. 115–130). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003212287-9>
- Plasma apolipoproteins: their role in cardiovascular diseases and usefulness of their blood concentration determination. Committee of the Study of Apolipoproteins, Italian Heart Foundation. (1997). *Cardiologia (Rome, Italy)*, 42 Suppl 1, 1–39. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/9147845>